

Synergistic Effects of Epoxy/PTFE/CNT Hybrid Nanocomposite Coating Against Silica Scaling and Corrosion Under Varying Geothermal Flow Conditions

Yurian Ariandi Andrameda ^{a,b}, Khasani ^{a,*}, Kusmono ^a, Hendra Ardi Kurniawan ^c, Herdian Ardi Febrianto ^c, Kadek Wahyudi ^a, Zaky Ahmad Aditya ^a, Shad Abdelmoumen Serroune ^d

^a Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Yogyakarta 55281, Indonesia

^b National Research and Innovation Agency, Puspiptek Area, Banten, 15314 Indonesia

^c PT Geo Dipa Energi (Persero) Aldevco Octagon 2nd Floor Jl Warung Jati Barat No. 75 Jakarta Selatan 12740, Indonesia

^d Nanogeios Laboratory - 5830 E 2nd St Suite 8, Casper, Wyoming USA 82609

Corresponding author: khasani@ugm.ac.id

Abstract.

This study presents the development of a multifunctional epoxy/polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)/carbon nanotube (CNT) hybrid nanocomposite coating designed to mitigate localized corrosion and silica scaling in harsh geothermal environments. Morphological and mechanical evaluations identified an optimal formulation (epoxy/PTFE40/CNT0.8) that successfully balances surface hydrophobicity (water contact angle of 139°) with superior adhesion strength (8.685 MPa), avoiding the nanoparticle agglomeration and structural defects observed at excessive filler loadings. Thermal analysis demonstrated that the integrated CNT network acts as a physical diffusion barrier, modifying the matrix degradation into a stabilized two-stage process capable of withstanding continuous exposure up to 150°C. Electrochemically, the optimized composite established a highly tortuous barrier against corrosive Cl⁻ ions, achieving a 94.05% protection efficiency and suppressing the corrosion rate to 0.0098 mm/year. Furthermore, the tailored micro-topography successfully prevented the mechanical interlocking of mineral deposits, delivering peak silica scaling reductions of 65.08% under hot geothermal conditions and maintaining a 50.92% mitigation efficacy during extreme cold supersaturation. Ultimately, this synergistic hybrid coating offers a robust, highly prospective

strategy for simultaneously combating dual degradation threats and extending the operational lifespan of geothermal infrastructure.

Keywords: Hybrid nanocomposite; silica scaling inhibition; corrosion protection; hydrophobic coating; geothermal

1. Introduction

Geothermal energy plays a vital role in the global transition toward renewable energy due to its sustainable nature and low carbon emissions (Alsaleh et al., 2023; Akhigbe, 2025; Khasani et al., 2021). However, the efficiency of geothermal power plants is often hindered by extreme material challenges in piping systems and heat exchangers (Penot et al., 2023; Zarrouk and Moon, 2014). Geothermal fluids carry a complex mixture of corrosive gases (H_2S , CO_2) and high concentrations of dissolved ions, particularly silica (SiO_2), which trigger rapid material degradation (Khasani et al., 2021; Nogara and Zarrouk, 2018). Infrastructure damage caused by corrosion and pipe blockages due to silica scaling not only drastically reduces heat transfer efficiency but also drives up operational costs resulting from frequent maintenance shutdowns and component replacements (Longval et al., 2024; Shannon, 1975; Zarrouk et al., 2014). Therefore, the development of coating materials capable of withstanding aggressive geothermal environments has become an urgent priority in current energy materials research.

The primary issue in geothermal piping applications is the synergistic phenomenon between corrosion and silica scale deposition (Hassani and Zheng, 2025), this phenomenon was shown in Figure 1. Corroded metal surfaces create a rough topography that serves as an ideal nucleation site for silica to precipitate and grow (Burstein and Vines, 2001; van den Heuvel et al., 2020). Conversely, the formed scale layer can create conditions for under-deposit corrosion, which exacerbates the rate of degradation of the base material (Lichti et al., 2024; Martelo et al., 2024). Figure 1b illustrated mechanism of the three-stage process for the growth

of a thin silica film from an aqueous solution. Nucleation, shows the attachment of aqueous silica particles to the substrate, then growth bumps where small nuclei have enlarged. Finally, these bumps have merged, and a continuous film has been formed (Van den Heuvel et al., 2018). Conventional mitigation methods, such as the use of chemical inhibitors, are often considered environmentally unfriendly and expensive (Spinthaki et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2023), while the use of corrosion-resistant metal alloys (such as titanium or high-alloy steel) is uneconomical for large-scale applications (Dacillo and Zarrouk, 2023). Consequently, organic polymer coatings, particularly epoxy resins, have been widely adopted due to their low cost, strong adhesion, and excellent chemical resistance (Jayakumari et al., 2023; Fanicchia and Karlsdottir, 2023; Sugama and Gawlik, 2002).

Fig. 1. (a) Photograph of silica scale deposition in a geothermal pipe and (b) schematic representation of the silica film formation mechanism.

Recent studies demonstrate that functional nanocomposite and ceramic/polymer coatings can significantly mitigate both silica scaling and corrosion, thereby allowing the substitution of expensive high-alloy materials with low-cost carbon steels in geothermal plants.

Recent studies are represented in Table 1. A 2023 review highlights various leading systems for geothermal scale and corrosion control, including TiO₂, SiO₂, fluorinated sol-gels, nickel-based coatings, graphene-modified polymers, iron borides, and high-entropy alloys. Specifically, ceramic TiO₂ and SiO₂(-FPS) coatings applied to stainless steel heat-exchanger plates have been shown to reduce fouling by ~30–48% and lower corrosion rates by ~60% in 150 °C simulated geothermal water (Fanicchia and Karlsdottir, 2023; Penot et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2020). Furthermore, advanced sol-gel nanocoatings containing CeO₂, Al₂O₃, ZnO, and TiO₂ nanoparticles decreased silica scaling by ~88% (from 0.42 to 0.05 mg cm⁻² h⁻¹) in 100 °C brine while simultaneously enhancing corrosion resistance (Serroune et al., 2024). Overall, multi-component ceramic/nanoparticle and nickel/boride-based coatings offer substantial value by cutting silica scaling by up to ~90% and lowering corrosion rates, although long-term field validation and comprehensive cost-benefit analyses remain limited (Fanicchia and Karlsdottir, 2023).

Table 1. Latest coating materials and performance for anti-scaling and anti corrosion in geothermal system.

Coating / material	Main function	Reported benefit / value	Citations
TiO ₂ , SiO ₂ , SiO ₂ -FPS sol-gel/LPD	Anti-scaling + anticorrosion	30–48% fouling reduction; ~60% lower corrosion vs 304 SS at 150 °C	(Fanicchia and Karlsdottir, 2023; Penot et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2020)
CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃ /ZnO/TiO ₂ nano-sol-gel	Anti-silica scaling + corrosion	~88% reduction in silica deposition at 100 °C	(Serroune et al., 2024)
Ni-P-PTFE electroless / duplex Ni-P-PTFE	Hydrophobic + anticorrosion	Highly hydrophobic, best corrosion	(Boakye et al., 2022; Karlsdottir et al., 2023)

		behavior in ORC hot brine (up to 80 °C)	
CoCrFeNiMo HEA, NiCrSiBFe, Fe-based amorphous	High-T corrosion protection	HEA shows highest corrosion resistance up to 250 °C in H ₂ S/CO ₂ brines	(Oppong Boakye et al., 2023)
Iron boride diffusion coatings	Corrosion + scaling resistance	Minimal scaling/corrosion in brines with SiO ₂ /Fe ₂ O ₃ ; withstand HPHT, acids	(Medvedovski, 2020)

Although epoxy is a popular coating candidate, the application of pure epoxy presents significant limitations in geothermal environments. Recent studies demonstrate that pure epoxy is susceptible to micro-crack initiation caused by shrinkage during the curing process, and exhibits limited barrier properties against the diffusion of water molecules and aggressive ions at elevated temperatures (Jayakumari et al., 2023; Xie et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2021). Furthermore, the hydroxyl groups on the epoxy chain render it hydrophilic, which inadvertently facilitates the adhesion of silica scale onto pipe surfaces (Ramakrishnan et al., 2022; Zhi et al., 2019). To address these issues, various researchers have modified epoxy with nanomaterials. The addition of Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) has been proven to enhance mechanical properties and corrosion resistance via the tortuous path mechanism (Han et al., 2009) whereas the incorporation of Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) is recognized for its effectiveness in reducing surface energy to provide anti-adhesion (non-stick) properties (Z. Li et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2022; Morita et al., 2018).

Although the potential of each individual filler is well-known, there is a distinct gap in the literature regarding the synergistic utilization of CNTs and PTFE within an epoxy matrix, particularly for geothermal applications. The majority of previous studies have focused

exclusively on a single type of filler—either enhancing corrosion resistance using CNTs alone (Deyab and Awadallah, 2020; Jeon et al., 2013) or improving hydrophobicity using PTFE alone (Fan et al., 2023). This single-filler approach is often inadequate, whereas CNTs alone do not provide sufficient self-cleaning or anti-scaling properties. To date, comprehensive investigations regarding the optimization of the Epoxy/PTFE/CNT hybrid ratio to achieve an optimal balance between corrosion protection (barrier effect) and silica scaling mitigation (hydrophobic effect) in simulated geothermal fluids remain highly limited.

This research aims to bridge this gap by developing and optimizing a hybrid Epoxy/PTFE/CNT nanocomposite coating. The novelty of this study lies in the design of a hybrid formulation that exploits these synergistic effects: CNTs function as mechanical reinforcement and a dense barrier against electrolyte diffusion, while PTFE is dispersed to minimize surface energy to repel silica deposition. This study not only conducts morphological and electrochemical characterizations but also performs compositional to identify the most effective formulation for withstanding corrosion rates while simultaneously minimizing silica scale formation under high-temperature conditions relevant to geothermal operations.

The results of this research are expected to provide significant contributions, both theoretically and practically. Theoretically, this study will deepen the understanding of the interaction mechanisms between carbon nanofillers and fluoropolymers within a thermoset matrix for extreme applications. Practically, this optimized coating formulation offers an economical, high-performance solution to extend the service life of geothermal piping infrastructure, reduce maintenance frequency, and ultimately enhance the overall efficiency of geothermal energy production.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

The polymer matrix consisted of epichlorohydrin bisphenol-A epoxy resin (Eposchon 1011A, Bakelite) cured with a cycloaliphatic amine curing agent (Eposchon 1011b, Bakelite); both components were supplied by PT. Justus Kimiaraya (Semarang, Indonesia). To functionalize the coating, two specific nanofillers were incorporated: polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, 99.9% purity, 260 nm particle size) to establish low surface energy, and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs, >96% purity, 8–18 nm diameter) to reinforce the structure. Both nanofillers were acquired from Nanografi (Turkey). To enhance the interfacial adhesion of the chemically inert PTFE within the epoxy matrix, a chemical etching pre-treatment was conducted using a solution of sodium metal (Na), naphthalene (C₁₀H₈), and tetrahydrofuran (THF). Processing solvents, including toluene, acetone, and xylene for dispersion control, as well as 96% ethanol, were purchased from Merck (Germany). ASTM A516 grade 70 carbon steel was selected as the substrate for this study due to its widespread application in high-pressure and high-temperature geothermal environments, ensuring the experimental conditions were representative of actual piping systems prone to corrosion and silica scaling.

2.2. Surface modification of PTFE

To mitigate the inherent chemical inertness of Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and improve its interfacial adhesion with the epoxy matrix, a surface modification was performed via a chemical etching process. A sodium-naphthalene complex etchant was prepared by dissolving sodium metal and naphthalene in 50 mL of tetrahydrofuran (THF) to yield a 1 M concentration. Subsequently, 10 g of PTFE nanopowder (260 nm) was introduced into the solution and agitated at 300 RPM for 10 minutes to ensure homogenous treatment. This process was utilized to facilitate electron delocalization on the fluoropolymer surface, thereby inducing the formation of unsaturated carbon-carbon bonds and polar functional groups (hydroxyl and carboxyl) upon hydrolysis. Following the reaction, the treated PTFE was rigorously rinsed with

deionized water at 90°C to eliminate residual reagents and quench the reaction. The resulting 1 M etched PTFE was subsequently employed as the reinforcing filler in the nanocomposite formulations. This process illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Surface Modification of PTFE flowchart.

2.3. Preparation of carbon steel substrate

Substrate Preparation ASTM A516 Grade 70 carbon steel plates were sectioned into coupons measuring 50 mm × 100 mm. The specimen surfaces were mechanically abraded using abrasive papers with grit sizes ranging from #100 to #1500, followed by polishing with an aluminum oxide-based compound to achieve a uniform surface finish. Prior to coating application, the polished substrates were degreased with alcohol to eliminate residual contaminants. This specific grade of steel was selected to replicate the material properties of industrial geothermal piping systems, ensuring the study remains relevant to high-pressure and high-temperature environments where corrosion and silica scaling are critical operational challenges.

2.4. Preparation of epoxy/PTFE/CNT precursor solution

The nanocomposite precursor was formulated by dispersing the nanofillers into 100 mL of toluene, as depicted in Figure 3. The concentrations of Treated Polytetrafluoroethylene (T-PTFE) and Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) were determined 40 wt% for T-PTFE and 0.8 and 2wt% for MWCNTs as shown in Table 2. Homogeneity was achieved through a

two-stage dispersion process: initially via mechanical stirring at 300 RPM for 2 hours, followed by probe ultrasonication for 30 minutes in an ice bath (2:2 cycle, ~5 kHz) to break down agglomerates. Once the fillers were fully dispersed, the epoxy resin was introduced. The mixture was then stirred at 300 RPM and heated at 80°C for 4 hours to promote solvent evaporation and matrix-filler interaction. Prior to application, the final viscosity was regulated by adding 25 wt% of the solvent.

Table 2. Experimental design composition of sample.

Name	Code	Matrix	PTFE (%wt)	CNT (%wt)
Bare Substrate	A0	Non Epoxy	-	-
Epoxy	A1	Epoxy	0	0
Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8	A2	Epoxy	40	0.8
Ep/PTFE40/CNT2	A3	Epoxy	40	2
Ep/PTFE20/CNT1	A4	Epoxy	20	1
Ep/PTFE40	B1	Epoxy	40	0
Ep/CNT2	B2	Epoxy	0	2

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram for precursor solution preparation.

2.5. Coating process of epoxy/PTFE/CNT nanocomposites

The application of the epoxy/PTFE/CNT nanocomposites was performed via a precision spray coating method. The coating formulation was prepared by mixing the precursor with the cycloaliphatic amine hardener (2:1 ratio) under gentle manual stirring for 2 minutes to prevent bubble formation. The mixture was subsequently sprayed onto pre-weighed ASTM A516 Grade 70 substrates using optimized operating conditions: an 8 bar compressor pressure, 2 bar spray pressure, 0.1 mm nozzle diameter, and a working distance of 10–15 cm. These parameters were selected to control droplet size and facilitate fine deposition, a critical factor for achieving superhydrophobicity. The curing process was conducted at room temperature (27°C) for 24 hours, after which the final mass was recorded to quantify the coating loading for subsequent testing.

2.6. Characterization

A comprehensive characterization was executed on the raw materials, substrate, and synthesized nanocomposite coatings using Water Contact Angle (WCA), adhesion strength, Shore D hardness, and surface roughness. The surface topography and physicochemical properties were comprehensively characterized through a series of standardized protocols. Surface roughness parameters (Ra, Rz, Rq) were recorded according to ISO 21920-2:2021 using a Mitutoyo SurfTest SJ-210 profilometer, while surface wettability and superhydrophobic stability were evaluated via the sessile drop method (ASTM D7490) using an Ossila Goniometer, with 10-second video analysis at 24 fps to monitor droplet dynamics. Furthermore, the interfacial bond integrity was quantified through pull-off adhesion testing in accordance with ASTM D4541 (2022) using an Elcometer 510, while the resistance to mechanical deformation was determined via Shore D hardness measurements (ASTM D2240) using a 4.5 kg load and a 15-second dwell time.

Microstructural mechanisms, including filler dispersion, were visualized through Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) using JEOL JSM-7001F. Thermal stability was evaluated using Differential Thermal Analysis and Thermogravimetric Analysis (DTA-TGA) on a Thermo Fisher instrument. The analysis was performed over a temperature range of 30°C to 800°C at a heating rate of 10 K/min under a nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL/min). While silica scaling rates were quantified using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES, PerkinElmer Avio 550). Finally, the functional performance was assessed through electrochemical, scaling rate, and spectroscopic methods corrosion rates were determined using a three-electrode system via Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) using 3.5% NaCl solution.

The corrosion rate was evaluated utilizing a dual-method approach comprising potentiodynamic polarization and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS). A standard three-electrode cell configuration was employed, consisting of a working electrode connected to the test specimen, an auxiliary (counter) electrode to facilitate current flow, and a reference electrode to establish a voltage datum also using 3.5% NaCl Solution. Through these potentiodynamic measurements, the electrochemical reaction kinetics were determined via Tafel extrapolation, wherein the relationship between the logarithmic current density (i) and the electrochemical potential (E) is graphically represented. From the resulting Tafel plots, the corrosion potential (E_{corr}) and corrosion current density (i_{corr}) were extracted via the intersection of the anodic and cathodic branches. To mitigate inherent inaccuracies associated with subjective slope selection, the extrapolation procedure was strictly executed by plotting the current density on a logarithmic scale and constructing tangent lines at a displacement of 50–100 mV from the E_{corr} value (Badea et al., 2010).

Fig. 4. Electrical circuit schematic: (a). without coating and, (b). with coating.

Following the determination of the E_{corr} and i_{corr} parameters, the corrosion rate, expressed in mils per year (mpy), was subsequently calculated according to the following equation based on ASTM Standard G59, 2003:

$$CR = 3.27 \times 10^{-3} \frac{I_{corr} EW}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

where:

CR : corrosion rate (mm per year)

EW : equivalent weight (gram)

I_{corr} : corrosion current density (mA/cm²)

ρ : density (g/cm³)

N : number of electrons lost per atom oxidized

Subsequently, the equivalent weight value was calculated using the following equation (ASTM Standard G102, 2015) :

$$EW = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{n_i \cdot f_i}{W_i}} \quad (2)$$

where:

EW : equivalent weight (gram)

n_i : Valence of the i-th element in the alloy

f_i : Mass fraction of the i-th element in the alloy

W_i : Atomic weight of the i-th element in the alloy

Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) was employed to evaluate the polarization resistance of the metal. The electrochemical impedance was measured across a predefined frequency range. A significant advantage of EIS is its utilization of a small-amplitude signal, which allows the measurement to be conducted without perturbing the intrinsic properties of the system under investigation (Hernández et al., 2020). The resistance of the corrosion product layer (R) is determined by the diameter of the semicircular arc projected onto the real axis. Furthermore, the electrolyte solution resistance (R_e) is identified as the distance from the origin ($x = 0$) to the high-frequency intercept, which corresponds to the lowest real impedance value. Electrical circuit schematic shown in Figure 4.

To characterize the silica scaling rate deposited within open channels, a plate immersion test was conducted. Several coated and uncoated steel plates were submerged in an open channel using steel wires and clips suspended from a U-shaped steel frame, strategically positioned to allow silica precipitation onto the surfaces (Figure 5). The experiment was carried out over a duration of 7 days, during which the mass of each plate was recorded daily, alongside the monitoring of pH, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), and temperature. The silica scales accumulated on the plate surfaces were subsequently collected and characterized using X-ray Diffraction (XRD) to determine the mineralogical properties, while Scanning Electron Microscopy combined with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (SEM-EDX) was utilized to analyze the morphology and elemental composition of the deposits.

Fig. 5. Silica scaling evaluation in geothermal brine water channels: (a). Schematic diagram and (b). Experimental setup.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Surface properties

Evaluating the synergistic effects of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) on the epoxy matrix, the surface properties of the synthesized hybrid nanocomposites were rigorously characterized. The optimization of these coatings is primarily governed by the interplay between chemical composition and morphological hierarchy. Surface wettability, quantified through water contact angle (WCA) measurements, and surface

roughness (Ra) were prioritized as the fundamental indicators of superhydrophobicity. Additionally, the mechanical integrity of the optimized films was assessed through adhesion strength and Shore D hardness testing to ensure the durability of the high-performance coatings under operational stresses.

Table 3. Experimental design matrix for material and epoxy/PTFE/CNT nanocomposites.

Sample		PTFE (%wt)	CNT (%wt)	Wettability (°)	Surface roughness (Ra [μm])	Adhesion strength (MPa)	Hardness (Shore D [HD])
No.	Code	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>RI</i>	<i>R2</i>	<i>R3</i>	<i>R4</i>
1	A0	0	0	92.51	0.036	-	-
2	A1	0	0	79.92	0.152	2.53	67.500
3	A2	40	0.8	139.110	4.945	8.685	73.550
4	A3	40	2	151.56	13.277	6.02	74.833

The experimental design matrix and the resulting physical responses for the epoxy/PTFE/CNT hybrid nanocomposites are systematically detailed in Table 3. Four distinct samples were analyzed, ranging from the bare substrate (A0) and neat epoxy (A1) to the reinforced hybrid systems containing a constant 40%wt PTFE with varying carbon nanotube (CNT) concentrations of 0.8%wt (A2) and 2%wt (A3). Initial characterization of the control samples A0 and A1 revealed water contact angles (WCA) of 92.51° and 79.92° , respectively, with baseline surface roughness Ra recorded at $0.036 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.152 \mu\text{m}$. Furthermore, mechanical properties for the neat epoxy (A1) were established with an adhesion strength of 2.53 MPa and a Shore D hardness value of 67.500.

Significant modifications to the surface and mechanical properties are observed upon the incorporation of the hydrophobic fillers into the epoxy matrix. In sample A2, the wettability is notably increased to 139.110° , while the Ra value rises to $4.945 \mu\text{m}$. A further transition toward superhydrophobicity is identified in sample A3, where a peak WCA of 151.56° and a maximum surface roughness of $13.277 \mu\text{m}$ are achieved. In terms of mechanical performance,

the Shore D hardness is progressively enhanced to 73.550 for A2 and 74.833 for A3. However, the adhesion strength, which initially increased to 8.685 MPa in sample A2, is found to decrease to 6.02 MPa in sample A3, indicating a complex interaction between the filler loading and the coating's interfacial integrity.

Fig. 6. Water contact angle images of substrate, epoxy, and nanocomposite coatings.

The visual evolution of surface wettability for the substrate, neat epoxy, and the formulated hybrid nanocomposite coatings is clearly illustrated by the droplet profiles in Figure 6. It can be observed that the neat epoxy coating (A1) exhibits an inherently hydrophilic nature with a water contact angle (WCA) of 79.92° , while the bare substrate (A0) demonstrates marginal hydrophobicity at 92.51° . These states are characterized by a noticeable spreading of the water droplets across the solid interface. Upon the incorporation of 40%wt PTFE and 0.8%wt CNT (sample A2), a significant transition toward a highly hydrophobic state is achieved, as evidenced by a WCA of 139.110° and a distinctly more spherical droplet shape. Furthermore, exceptional superhydrophobicity is successfully attained in sample A3, which is formulated with 40%wt PTFE and an increased CNT loading of 2%wt, recording a peak WCA of 151.56° . This remarkable enhancement in water repellency is primarily attributed to the synergistic effect between the inherently low surface energy provided by the fluorinated PTFE matrix and the hierarchical micro/nano-scale roughness induced by the dispersed CNT network. As extensively discussed in relevant literature (Han et al., 2009; Parry et al., 2012),

such multi-scale structural configurations facilitate the transition of the droplet from the Wenzel state to a stable Cassie-Baxter wetting regime. In this regime, air pockets are effectively entrapped within the rough interstitial spaces of the nanocomposite, substantially minimizing the actual contact area between the water droplet and the solid surface, thereby driving the contact angle beyond the 150° superhydrophobic threshold.

Fig. 7. 2D surface roughness profiles of the substrate and epoxy, and nanocomposite coatings.

The morphological evolution of the formulated coatings is further elucidated by the 2D surface roughness profiles presented in Figure 7. It is clearly depicted that the bare substrate (A0) and the neat epoxy coating (A1) exhibit predominantly smooth topographies, characterized by minimal amplitude fluctuations constrained within a sub-micron vertical range. This visual observation is quantitatively supported by the exceptionally low average surface roughness (Ra) values of $0.036 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.152 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. Upon the incorporation of 40%wt PTFE and 0.8%wt CNT (sample A2), a distinct alteration in the surface architecture

is observed. The linear profile of A2 reveals significant topological fluctuations with vertical amplitudes expanding to approximately $\pm 15.4 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to a marked increase in the calculated average roughness R_a to $4.945 \mu\text{m}$. Interestingly, as the CNT concentration is further increased to 2%wt in sample A3, the topography undergoes another distinct structural transformation. Although the maximum vertical amplitude of the asperities remains comparable to A2 (spanning approximately $\pm 13.4 \mu\text{m}$), the spatial distribution of the peaks and valleys becomes significantly more uniform, dense, and periodically structured. This specific hierarchical arrangement and increased asperity frequency across the measured surface result in a higher cumulative average roughness, yielding the peak R_a value of $13.277 \mu\text{m}$. The generation of this highly textured micro/nano-morphology is deemed critical, as it provides the essential physical roughness required to entrap air and sustain the robust superhydrophobic state observed in the contact angle measurements.

The mechanical integrity of the synthesized coatings was subsequently assessed through Shore D hardness and adhesion strength measurements to evaluate their durability for practical applications. A baseline adhesion strength of 2.53 MPa and a Shore D hardness of 67.500 were established for the neat epoxy control (A1). Following the incorporation of 40%wt PTFE and 0.8%wt CNT in sample A2, a pronounced enhancement in mechanical properties was observed, wherein the adhesion strength peaked at 8.685 MPa and the hardness increased to 73.550. This strengthening mechanism is generally attributed to the effective load transfer and crack-bridging capabilities provided by a well-dispersed carbon nanotube network within the polymer matrix (Qian et al., 2000). Nevertheless, a divergent mechanical response was recorded when the CNT loading was further elevated to 2%wt (sample A3). Although the Shore D hardness was marginally improved to a maximum of 74.833, reflecting the inherent stiffness imparted by the higher volume fraction of nanoparticles, the adhesion strength was found to significantly deteriorate to 6.02 MPa (Li et al., 2023; Rachid et al., 2024). This degradation in

interfacial bonding is commonly hypothesized to result from excessive nanoparticle agglomeration at higher loading concentrations; such agglomerates can act as localized stress concentration points and physically impede the optimal cross-linking of the epoxy binder at the substrate interface (Ashraf et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2022), thereby highlighting a critical trade-off between maximizing superhydrophobic roughness and maintaining coating adhesion.

The comprehensive evaluation of the synthesized hybrid nanocomposites successfully establishes a critical structure-property relationship, wherein surface wettability and mechanical integrity are highly dependent on the synergistic interaction of the incorporated fillers (Afolabi and Ndou, 2024). The observed transition to a robust superhydrophobic regime is fundamentally governed by the Cassie-Baxter wetting model (Parry et al., 2012); the intrinsically low surface energy imparted by the fluorinated polymer (Kim et al., 2021), coupled with the hierarchical micro/nanoscale roughness induced by the carbon nanotube network (Jung et al., 2018), facilitates the entrapment of stable air pockets that effectively minimize the solid-liquid interfacial contact area (Suroń et al., 2025). Concurrently, the mechanical characterization elucidates a pronounced performance trade-off dictated by nanoparticle dispersion dynamics. While the inherent rigidity of the dispersed fillers enhances the overall coating hardness through effective load-transfer mechanisms, excessive nanoparticle loading is observed to induce severe phase agglomeration. Based on established composite failure theories, these agglomerates act as localized stress concentrators and physically disrupt the interfacial cross-linking density of the polymer binder at the substrate level, thereby degrading adhesion (Zeinedini et al., 2025). Consequently, it is deduced that the ultimate efficacy of these high-performance coatings relies on achieving a delicate architectural equilibrium; the formulation must be strategically optimized to provide sufficient multi-scale roughness for superior water repellency without compromising the essential interfacial bonding strength required for durable engineering applications (Andrameda et al., 2026).

Surface morphological examinations were conducted to evaluate the spatial distribution and interfacial interactions between the polymer matrix and the hybrid fillers. Based on the FE-SEM micrographs (Figure 8) of composite D (Epoxy/PTFE40/CNT0.8), the surface topography exhibits a heterogeneous distribution characterized by two distinct types of nanofillers with contrasting geometries. At lower magnification (10,000x), the surface appears relatively uniform; however, closer inspection reveals the presence of spherical particle agglomerations and dispersed filamentous structures.

Fig. 8. FE-SEM surface morphology of the A2 Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 at (a) 10,000x and (b) 30,000x magnification.

Upon increasing the magnification to 30,000x, these architectural details become more pronounced: the large globular particles are identified as PTFE agglomerates (Li et al., 2023), whereas the entwined, thread-like filaments represent the CNT network. Despite the high PTFE loading (40 wt%), this phase tends to form micro/sub-micro clusters, which may act as structural defects or stress concentrators, thereby limiting effective interfacial contact with the epoxy matrix. Conversely, the CNTs (0.8 wt%) are observed forming a delicate interconnected network distributed between the PTFE agglomerates and the epoxy phase. This morphology indicates that while macro-scale dispersion at 10,000x is deemed sufficiently homogeneous, idealized molecular-level dispersion at the nano-scale has not been fully achieved—a condition

known to influence the overall mechanical response and tribological characteristics of the composite (Zhang et al., 2018).

3.2. Thermal properties

Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), collectively referred to as Simultaneous Thermal Analysis (STA), were conducted on the synthesized nanocomposite samples across a broad temperature range of 20 to 800°C. These analyses were performed to systematically characterize the overall thermal stability and to detect the distinct phase transitions within the nanocomposite systems. Through the obtained TGA profiles, the sequential stages of thermal degradation and the final residual mass fraction (char yield) were determined, thereby elucidating the effect of the incorporated nanofillers (PTFE and CNT) on the thermal degradation resistance of the epoxy matrix. Concurrently, the corresponding DSC curves were utilized to identify the endothermic and exothermic energy alterations associated with specific thermal events, such as the glass transition temperature (T_g), melting phenomena, or residual curing reactions. Consequently, critical insights into the thermodynamic properties of the engineered composite materials were established.

As illustrated by the Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) profiles in Figure 9, the thermal degradation of all epoxy nanocomposite samples was observed to proceed through two primary stages. The process was initiated by the release of moisture and low-molecular-weight volatile compounds below 200°C, which was subsequently followed by the degradation of the main polymer backbone. A significant mass decomposition was exhibited by the neat epoxy (A1) starting at approximately 300°C, ultimately resulting in a char yield of approximately 35 wt% at 800°C. This thermal behavior is notably contrasted by the binary composite systems (Bandeira et al., 2017). Upon the incorporation of 40 wt% PTFE (B1), a distinct reduction in thermal stability at intermediate temperatures was recorded. This phenomenon is attributed to

the relatively lower decomposition temperature of the fluorinated polymer, which induced a rapid initial mass loss and yielded a reduced final char residue (≈ 25 wt%) (Pan et al., 2016). Conversely, superior thermal stability was demonstrated by the CNT-reinforced composite (B2), as evidenced by the highest relative curve position and a maximum residual mass exceeding 40 wt%. This observation confirms the efficacy of carbon nanotubes acting as a robust thermal barrier network (Satish et al., 2017).

Fig. 9. TGA thermograms of the baseline epoxy and the epoxy/PTFE/CNT nanocomposites.

The detailed thermal phenomena corresponding to these degradation profiles are summarized in Table 4. For the neat epoxy, the thermal degradation process is generally characterized by two distinct stages: the initial volatilization of absorbed moisture, residual solvents, or unreacted curing agents at temperatures below 200°C, followed by the dominant decomposition of the main epoxy polymer chains within the temperature range of 300–500°C. This primary degradation phase generates gaseous byproducts and leaves a carbonaceous char residue at temperatures exceeding 500°C (Gu and Liang, 2003). Interestingly, a distinct three-

stage degradation profile was exhibited by the Ep/PTFE composite. While the initial volatilization below 200°C and the subsequent epoxy degradation between 300–500°C proceeded similarly to the neat resin, a third significant weight loss event was induced by the incorporated Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) filler at a higher temperature range of 500–600°C. In this upper-temperature regime, the complete depolymerization and volatilization of PTFE into tetrafluoroethylene (TFE) monomers occur, thereby restricting the final residual mass solely to the epoxy-derived char (Sahli et al., 2017). Meanwhile, an overall enhancement in the thermal stability of the matrix was demonstrated by the Carbon Nanotube (CNT) reinforced composite (Ep/CNT). The incorporated CNTs are hypothesized to act as physical barriers that reinforce the protective char layer, consequently elevating the degradation temperature of the epoxy phase (Mirzapour et al., 2024). As a result, the structural matrix is rendered significantly more resistant to high-temperature exposure compared to its neat epoxy counterpart (Bao et al., 2021).

Table 4. Thermal degradation characteristics of the neat epoxy and its PTFE/CNT composites derived from TGA analysis (Bandeira et al., 2017; Pan et al., 2016; Satish et al., 2017).

Epoxy	< 200°C	Loss of volatiles (moisture, residual solvent, unreacted curing agent)
	300–500 °C	Degradation of the epoxy polymer main chain
	>500 °C	Epoxy char residue
Ep/PTFE	< 200°C	Loss of volatiles (moisture, residual solvent, unreacted curing agent)
	300–500 °C	Degradation of the epoxy polymer main chain
	500-600 °C	Degradation of Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) via depolymerization into TFE monomers (completely volatilized/evaporated)
	>500 °C	Epoxy char residue
Ep/CNT	Overall	Makes the epoxy matrix more resistant to thermal degradation

The thermal stability dynamics exhibited by the DOE hybrid composites (A2, A3, and A4) are dictated by a competitive interplay between the detrimental thermal effects of PTFE and the stabilizing influence of the CNTs (Mirzapour et al., 2024). Samples formulated with lower filler concentrations, specifically the A4 formulations, were observed to possess lower thermal stability compared to the neat epoxy. This indicates that at these specific constituent ratios, the destabilizing effect of the incorporated PTFE is dominant over the matrix. This phenomenon is further corroborated by the observation that the degradation peak of PTFE predominates at temperatures overlapping with the decomposition of the epoxy matrix. However, upon a significant increase in the filler loading (both PTFE and CNT) in the A3 and A2 samples, the stability profiles were notably improved, surpassing the residual curve of the neat epoxy at temperatures exceeding 550°C.

This enhanced thermal stability in the optimized A2 and A3 samples is primarily attributed to the presence of CNTs, which function as an effective physical diffusion barrier. The dispersed CNT network within the matrix hinders the release of volatile byproducts generated during the epoxy decomposition, thereby retarding the degradation rate and effectively increasing the final char residue (Bao et al., 2021). Although elevated PTFE concentrations accelerate degradation at initial temperatures, the integration of CNTs at an appropriate ratio is proven to successfully compensate for this thermal deficit. Consequently, the TGA analysis definitively demonstrates that CNTs act as a crucial component in the thermal stabilization of the epoxy nanocomposites. An optimal combination of PTFE and CNT loadings yields a more balanced and robust thermal performance relative to the neat epoxy matrix. Based on these findings, it is recommended that the optimal composite formulation (A2) be restricted to a safe maximum operating temperature below 300°C to preserve the structural integrity of the epoxy matrix and prevent primary polymer degradation.

Based on the Simultaneous Thermal Analysis (STA) presented in Figure 10 comprising the DSC and the TGA curve for the neat epoxy sample (A1) critical thermal characteristics can be systematically identified. A stable mass profile up to approximately 300°C is exhibited by the TGA curve. The primary thermal degradation, indicated by a steep mass reduction in the TGA profile, is initiated beyond this threshold, thereby defining the absolute thermal stability limit of the material. Simultaneously, a distinct exothermic peak at a maximum temperature of 342.30°C is revealed by the DSC curve. This prominent exothermic peak generally corresponds to the severe thermal decomposition or oxidative degradation of the epoxy polymer matrix. The presence of this substantial exothermic event, perfectly overlapping with the significant mass loss observed in the TGA, confirms that the epoxy matrix undergoes critical structural failure at this specific temperature, accompanied by the release of thermal energy. Meanwhile, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the epoxy, which is inherently an endothermic transition, is expected to be observed at a considerably lower temperature range prior to degradation.

Fig. 10. Simultaneous thermal analysis (STA) profiles for the neat epoxy matrix and the nanocomposite A3, comprising (a) DSC and (b) TGA curves.

As illustrated in Figure 10, the thermal characteristics of the epoxy matrix and its nanocomposite (A3) were comprehensively evaluated through Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA). Based on the DSC profiles in Figure 10(a), two significant thermal energy anomalies are identified within the A3 sample, indicating a distinct modification of the decomposition pathway. A sharp exothermic peak is observed with a maximum at 322.74°C within the temperature range of 282.27 to 374.57°C, which is primarily attributed to the initial thermal degradation and chain scission of the epoxy matrix. This exothermic nature suggests the occurrence of oxidative decomposition or high-energy cross-linking completion prior to total structural failure (Levchik and Weil, 2004; Torrecillas et al., 1996). Furthermore, a broader secondary exothermic peak is detected between 500 and 600°C, a feature notably absent in the neat epoxy profile. This second stage is hypothesized to originate from the advanced decomposition of the PTFE filler, coupled with the oxidation of carbonaceous char residues that have been structurally stabilized by the CNT network. The presence of these two distinct peaks substantiates that the thermal decomposition pathway has been successfully transformed into a more robust, two-stage process through the synergistic effect of the nanofillers.

In correlation with the DSC data, the TGA profiles in Figure 10(b) provide quantitative evidence of the modified mass loss kinetics and enhanced thermal stability. For the nanocomposite (A3), an initial mass loss (Δm) of -5.822% is recorded between 46.86 and 205.14°C, corresponding to the evaporation of moisture and light volatiles, leaving a remaining mass of 94.711%. The primary degradation phase for the A3 sample is observed at higher temperatures compared to the initial stages of the neat epoxy, eventually resulting in a final remaining mass of 24.463% at 802.16°C. In contrast, the neat epoxy (A1) exhibits a more drastic primary mass loss of -56.321% within the 237.97 to 810.41°C range. The shift of

degradation onset toward higher temperatures and the formation of a more stable char layer in sample A3 confirm the role of CNTs as a physical barrier that inhibits the diffusion of volatile degradation products. Ultimately, the integration of PTFE and CNTs is shown to promote a protective char-forming mechanism (Zheng et al., 2015), significantly improving the overall thermal resistance of the hybrid nanocomposite.

3.3. Corrosion rate analysis

3.3.1. Electrochemical corrosion rate measurement via three-electrode potentiostat system

Based on the Tafel polarization curves comparing the bare substrate, neat epoxy (A1), Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2), and the Ep/PTFE40/CNT2 (A3), formulation, it can be concluded that the corrosion kinetics of the steel substrate are significantly altered by the application of the nanocomposite coatings. The fundamental relationship between the applied electrode potential and the logarithm of the current density, which inherently reflects the corrosion rate, is illustrated by these Tafel curves. An enhancement in overall corrosion resistance is indicated by a shift of the corrosion potential (E_{corr}) towards more positive, noble values (higher on the Y-axis) and a concurrent shift of the corrosion current density (i_{corr}) to the left (lower on the X-axis).

The corresponding Tafel polarization curves are presented in Figure 11. The initial analysis reveals that the most negative E_{corr} (approximately -0.53 V) and the highest i_{corr} (positioned farthest to the right) are exhibited by the bare substrate, thereby confirming the highest corrosion rate and a severe susceptibility to anodic dissolution. Following the application of the neat epoxy coating (A1), the E_{corr} is successfully shifted to a more noble potential (approximately -0.336 V) and the i_{corr} is substantially reduced, demonstrating the fundamental function of the neat epoxy as a passive physical barrier. Significantly, the E_{corr}

is shifted to a value nearly identical to that of A0 (~ -0.326 V) by the optimal Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) coating (green line), while simultaneously achieving the lowest i_{corr} (positioned farthest to the left) among all evaluated samples. This firmly establishes that the electrochemical corrosion rate is most effectively suppressed by this optimized hybrid formulation.

Conversely, a less optimal electrochemical response compared to Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) is demonstrated by the Ep/PTFE40/CNT2 (A3) as evidenced by its Tafel curve (blue line) being positioned intermediately between those of A0 and Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2). A slightly more active/negative E_{corr} (-0.354 V) compared to both A1 and Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) alongside a comparatively higher i_{corr} than that of Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2), is recorded for the A3. This observation is highly consistent with prior morphological analyses, suggesting that the critical threshold for nanofiller concentration is likely exceeded in the A3 formulation. It is hypothesized that such excessive filler loading induces severe phase agglomeration, which subsequently creates structural micro-defects and conductive pathways within the coating layer. Consequently, its efficacy as an impermeable corrosion barrier is significantly compromised when compared to the meticulously Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) nanocomposite.

Fig. 11. Tafel polarization curves of the bare substrate and the epoxy/PTFE/CNT composite coatings in a 3.5 wt% NaCl solution.

The quantitative Tafel corrosion test results, presented in Table 5, corroborate the electrochemical trends observed in the polarization curves (Figure 11), wherein the corrosion rate of the underlying substrate is superiorly mitigated by the Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) formulation. The highest corrosion rate ($CR = 0.165$ mm/year), coupled with the maximum corrosion current density ($I_{corr} = 101.573$ $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) and the most negative corrosion potential ($E_{corr} = -537.157$ mV), is exhibited by the uncoated bare substrate, thereby confirming a high thermodynamic susceptibility to anodic dissolution. Upon the application of the neat epoxy coating (A1), the I_{corr} is drastically reduced to 9.316 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, and the E_{corr} is shifted to a more noble -336.251 mV, yielding a protection efficiency of 90.83%. However, the optimal anti-corrosion performance is demonstrated by the Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) nanocomposite, which records the lowest I_{corr} (6.043 $\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) and the minimum overall corrosion rate (0.0098 mm/year), culminating in the highest protection efficiency of 94.05%. This superior barrier performance is attributed to the synergistic combination of PTFE (which significantly enhances surface hydrophobicity) and CNTs (which fortify the internal coating integrity) (R. Zhang et al., 2024). Together, an exceptionally dense and robust physical barrier against Cl^- ions and water penetration is established by these integrated components (Ying et al., 2020).

Table 5. Tafel corrosion test results in 3.5% NaCl solution.

Sample	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	E (mV)	CR (mm/year)	Effectivity (%)
Substrate (A0)	101.573	-537.157	0.165	0.00
Epoxy (A1)	9.316	-336.251	0.015	90.80
Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2)	6.043	-326.581	0.010	94.05

Ep/PTFE40/CNT2 (A3)	15.887	-354.775	0.026	84.36
---------------------	--------	----------	-------	-------

The behavioral discrepancy between the bare substrate and the formulated coatings can be elucidated by the underlying protection mechanisms. Due to the complete absence of a physical barrier, unhindered anodic and cathodic reactions are permitted to occur freely on the bare steel surface, resulting in the highly accelerated I_{corr} . Conversely, the neat epoxy (A1) functions as a passive barrier, significantly restricting the interfacial contact area between the corrosive electrolyte and the metallic substrate, thereby suppressing the corrosion kinetics by over 90% (Chopra et al., 2022). The subsequent enhancement observed from A1 to the optimized Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) formulation is driven directly by the nanocomposite integration: the internal compactness of the coating is improved, and the tortuous path for permeating corrosive species is significantly extended by the dispersion of CNTs at an optimal concentration of 0.8% (Jeon et al., 2013). In contrast, a higher I_{corr} ($15.887 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) and a diminished protection efficiency (84.36%) relative to both A1 and Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) are exhibited by the Ep/PTFE40/CNT2 (A3). This substantiates the hypothesis that the critical dispersion threshold is exceeded by the nanofiller concentration in A3. Consequently, severe internal agglomeration is triggered, generating structural micro-defects and establishing rapid conductive pathways for the electrolyte, which inherently degrades the barrier functionality (Huang et al., 2024).

Although an exceptionally high protection efficiency (reaching 94.05% in corrosion suppression) is demonstrated by the Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) absolute (100%) protection cannot be practically attained due to the intrinsic properties of the organic matrix itself. The primary limitation in achieving total isolation is governed by inherent water and ion permeability. A certain degree of permeability is possessed by all polymeric networks, allowing water molecules and aggressive ions (Cl^-) to progressively penetrate and be absorbed into the film structure (water uptake) over prolonged exposure periods (Deflorian et al., 2010;

Deflorian and Rossi, 2006). The barrier properties of the coating are gradually compromised by this continuous penetration, ultimately permitting the corrosive species to reach the metal-coating interface and initiate localized faradaic reactions. Furthermore, unavoidable micro-defects or porosities generated during the coating application process, alongside minor surface degradation incurred during the electrochemical testing, serve as accelerated ingress pathways for the bulk electrolyte. Even though the macroscopic corrosion rate has been suppressed to a minimal threshold, the persistence of residual corrosion that cannot be entirely eradicated by the polymeric coating signifies that the electrochemical degradation process is continuously, albeit slowly, proceeding (Liu et al., 2013).

3.3.2. EIS measurement

The Nyquist plots presented in Figure 12, obtained from Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements, clearly visualize the discrepancies in corrosion resistance among the samples through the diameter of the semicircular arcs. In this context, a larger arc diameter is directly proportional to higher impedance and resistance. The bare steel substrate exhibited the smallest arc (terminating before $\approx 300 \Omega$), confirming its inherent susceptibility to corrosive attack. The application of neat epoxy (A1) significantly enhanced the resistance, with the arc diameter reaching approximately 800Ω , which results from the fundamental insulating function of the epoxy matrix. However, the A2 nanocomposite demonstrated the most superior performance, characterized by the largest semicircular arc exceeding 1000Ω . This dramatic increase in impedance substantiates that the optimized coating formulation, integrated with PTFE and CNT, has successfully established a superior barrier protection system that effectively prevents electrolyte penetration and suppresses the corrosion rate (Ying et al., 2020).

Fig. 12. Nyquist plots of the bare substrate and the synthesized hybrid nanocomposite coatings.

The quantitative results derived from fitting the EIS data using an equivalent circuit model are summarized in the Table 6, where each component represents a specific electrochemical or physical process at the coating/solution interface. R_s (Solution Resistance) denotes the intrinsic resistance of the bulk electrolyte. C_f (Film Capacitance) represents the dielectric capacity of the intact coating layer, a value that typically increases upon water uptake, while R_f (Resistance of Film) indicates the resistance offered by the coating to ionic transport through its porous structure. Furthermore, C_{dl} (Double Layer Capacitance) refers to the capacitance formed at the substrate/electrolyte interface upon the onset of corrosion, and R_{ct} (Charge Transfer Resistance) represents the resistance against electrochemical charge transfer at the metallic surface. The R_{ct} value serves as the most direct indicator of a material's corrosion resistance.

Table 6. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) parameters for the bare substrate and composite coatings in a 3.5 wt% NaCl solution.

Sample	Rs (ohm)	Cf (F)	Rf (ohm)	Cdl (F)	Rct (ohm)
Substrate (A0)	4.066	5.07×10^{-06}	280.3		
Epoxy (A1)	53.71	1.79×10^{-05}	199.4	4.38×10^{-4}	600.6
A2	42.25	4.01×10^{-05}	187.4	3.92×10^{-4}	882.9

A quantitative comparison of Rct values demonstrates that the Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) coating provides far superior corrosion protection compared to the neat epoxy, the bare substrate, and the other coatings detailed in Table 6. The bare steel substrate lacked a measurable Rct (assuming immediate corrosion), with a film resistance (Rf) of only 280.3 Ω. Neat epoxy (A1) exhibited an Rct of 600.6 Ω, reflecting the resistance to charge transfer following moisture penetration. Most notably, the Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) composite yielded the highest Rct of 882.9 Ω. This increase of approximately 47% compared to the neat epoxy proves that the incorporation of nanofillers successfully reinforces the interface and inhibits the electron transfer processes that drive corrosion. Consequently, it is established that the Ep/PTFE40/CNT0.8 (A2) composite represents the coating formulation with the lowest corrosion rate.

3.4. Silica rate analysis

3.4.1. ICP-OES analysis and physicochemical characterization of geothermal brine

Based on the geothermal brine composition data from Wellpad 28 and Wellpad 30 presented in Table 7, as well as the experimental conditions at Wellpad 7, the primary investigation into silica scaling must be focused on Silicon (Si) concentration and pH levels, as the solubility of SiO₂ is highly dependent on these two parameters. At Wellpad 28, a

significantly high Si concentration (1104.54 ppm) was recorded at a near-neutral pH (6.86), rendering the system highly susceptible to amorphous silica precipitation as the temperature decreases (specifically from 80.6°C to 78°C). Although the initial pH and Si data for Wellpad 30 at zero distance are unavailable, data from distances of 80 m and 150 m indicate a pH reduction from 6.14 to 5.9 and a temperature drop from 87.2°C to 68.3°C, resulting from acidization treatment. This acidification process, while lowering the pH, theoretically increases the propensity for silica scaling, as amorphous silica exhibits minimum solubility under acidic conditions (pH < 7).

Table 7. Composition and properties of the brine water.

No	Element (ppm)	Wellpad 28	Wellpad 30		Range	Temp. (°C)	pH
1	Si	1104.54	1073.21		Wellpad 28		
2	B	529.39	511.77		0	80.6	6.86
3	Ca	41.96	44.95		4	78.8	7
4	Fe	NA	NA		8	78	6.86
5	K	2727.49	2788.57				
6	Li	82.38	82.94		Range	Temp. (°C)	pH
7	Mg	0.43	0.13		Wellpad 30		
8	Na	8482.82	8676.25		0	87.2	6.14
9	P	NA	NA		80	73.3	6.02
10	Si	68.72	35.93		150	68.3	5.9
Wellpad 7							
		Temperature (°C)			pH		Flow speed (m/s)
	Hot Condition	93.35 ± 0.71			5.31 ± 0.22		0.106
	Cold Condition	82.56 ± 0.58			5.31 ± 0.17		0.389

Nevertheless, the acidization treatment at Wellpad 30 successfully achieved a drastic reduction in Si levels post-processing (decreasing from 1073.21 ppm at the surface to 35.93 ppm at a depth of 150 m), indicating the efficacy of the acidification method in reducing the overall availability of Si ions. Other constituent factors, such as high Sodium (Na) content (~8400 ppm) and substantial Potassium (K) levels (~2700 ppm), contribute to increased salinity and water conductivity, thereby exacerbating the corrosion potential even if they are not

directly involved in the silica scaling mechanism. Consequently, an ideal coating for both wellpads must address the challenge of corrosion resistance necessitated by high Na/K concentrations while simultaneously providing a hydrophobic surface to mitigate the adhesion of silica scales triggered by critical temperature shifts and pH fluctuations, particularly in the non-acidified environment of Wellpad 28.

3.4.2. Characterization and evaluation of silica scale deposition

X-ray Diffraction (XRD) analysis of the scales extracted from the geothermal brine (Figure 13) indicates that the formed silica predominantly exists in an amorphous phase. This characteristic is confirmed by the presence of a broad "hump" or a wide, low-intensity slope centered at approximately $2\theta = 22.5873^\circ$ (consistent with ICSD 98-016-2660), which is a diagnostic feature of the non-crystalline SiO_2 structure. Nevertheless, a sharp diffraction peak with maximum intensity was also observed at $2\theta = 31.6397^\circ$, identified as Aluminum Oxide (Al_2O_3) in accordance with ICSD 98-002-8920 (Vicente et al., 2010). The presence of Al_2O_3 is further corroborated by X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) analysis, which detected an Al_2O_3 content of 0.9% within the scale (Ishmah et al., 2020). Although the scale composition is dominated by SiO_2 , reaching 90.8% as shown in the XRF results in Table 8, a moderate crystallinity of 52.1% was recorded. This suggests that the scale is not purely amorphous silica but rather a composite material consisting of an amorphous SiO_2 phase and minor crystalline phases of secondary minerals.

Fig. 13. XRD patterns of the collected silica scaling deposits.

Table 8. Elemental composition of silica scaling deposits determined by XRF analysis.

Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Cl	Fe ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	MgO	P ₂ O ₅	SiO ₂	S
0.9%	0.5%	4.4%	0.5%	0.9%	0.3%	1.0%	90.8%	0.4%

Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FE-SEM) analysis in Figure 14 (at 25,000x magnification) reveals the accumulation of deposited particles on the coating surface. These particles exhibit a nodular and agglomerated morphology, which is highly characteristic of amorphous silica scales that grow via polymerization within supersaturated fluids. The identity of these deposits is definitively confirmed by Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) data, showing a chemical composition dominated by Silicon (Si) at 51.47 wt% and Oxygen (O) at 40.79 wt%. This combined total of 92.26 wt% indicates a predominant SiO₂ structure. The presence of minor elements such as Chlorine (Cl) at 6.20 wt% and Sodium (Na) at 1.55 wt% indicates residual ions from the geothermal brine trapped within the deposit matrix. Thus, it is comprehensively proven that the particles observed in the FESEM micrographs are indeed silica scaling deposits.

Fig. 14. Surface morphology of silica scaling deposits observed via FE-SEM at magnifications of (a) 1,000x and (b) 25,000x.

3.4.3. Silica scaling rate

The silica scaling rate evaluation of the nanocomposites was comprehensively conducted over a 5-day period to assess coating effectiveness under simulated harsh geothermal environments. The experimental methodology involved the variation of two primary parameters: temperature (hot at $93.35 \pm 0.71^\circ\text{C}$ and cold at $82.56 \pm 0.58^\circ\text{C}$) and inclination angle (0° and 45°). This study aimed to compare the anti-scaling performance across four sample types: the bare steel substrate (A0), neat epoxy (A1), the A2, and A3. Visual comparison of silica scaling accumulation on the bare steel substrate and the coated plates shown in Table 9.

Table 9. Visual comparison of silica scaling accumulation on the bare steel substrate and the coated plates at a 0° (horizontal) inclination.

<i>Bare Steel Substrate</i>					
Cold Temperature			Hot Temperature		
Day 1	Day 3	Day 5	Day 1	Day 3	Day 5
<i>Nanocomposit D</i>					
Cold Temperature			Hot Temperature		
Day 1	Day 3	Day 5	Day 1	Day 3	Day 5

Figures 15 and 16 illustrate the silica scaling rate profiles at an inclination of 45° and 0°, respectively. This clearly demonstrated that under lower temperature conditions, the average deposition rate at an inclination of 45° is lower than that at 0° (horizontal) across all samples. This phenomenon is attributed to the increased shear stress on inclined surfaces, which more effectively cleans or inhibits scale adhesion (Loureiro et al., 2023). Furthermore, the bare steel substrate and neat epoxy (control) consistently exhibited the highest scaling rates compared to the two nanocomposites (A2 and A3). This significant discrepancy arises because the steel substrate and neat epoxy are hydrophilic (low WCA), which increases the surface adhesion energy and facilitates the attachment, nucleation, and growth of amorphous silica. Conversely, the A2 composite, characterized by a WCA of 139°, demonstrated the lowest scaling rate, validating that enhancing hydrophobicity is the most effective strategy for mitigating silica scaling in geothermal environments (Longval et al., 2024).

Fig. 15. Silica scaling rates and corresponding regression fitting under various experimental conditions: (a). Hot 0°, (b). Cold 0°, (c). Hot 45°, and (d). Cold 45°.

The discrepancy in scaling rates between the A2 and A3 formulation, despite both possessing hydrophobic characteristics, can be elucidated through the interaction between the Water Contact Angle (WCA) and surface roughness. The A2 composite was optimally designed with a high WCA and a smoother roughness profile, facilitating a true lotus effect characterized by organized micro- and nano-structures. In contrast, while the A3 is also hydrophobic, it tends to exhibit a higher, non-optimal roughness that can create "dead spots" or traps where scale can accumulate and stabilize its adhesion, particularly under static or low-flow conditions (Azimi et al., 2014; van den Heuvel et al., 2020). Consequently, the A3 showed

a higher scaling rate than the A2 formulation because scale accumulation occurs more readily and rapidly on its coarser, less homogeneous surface morphology.

Furthermore, the silica scaling rate in geothermal brine environments is heavily influenced by temperature and flow dynamics (shear stress), which explains the rate variations across the hot, cold, 0°, and 45° conditions. Generally, the cold condition resulted in significantly higher scaling rates compared to the hot condition for all samples. This is due to the fact that under cold conditions, the solubility of amorphous silica decreases drastically, creating high supersaturation—the primary thermodynamic driver for silica precipitation. Conversely, under hot conditions, silica solubility remains high, maintaining the fluid in a stable or only slightly supersaturated state (Zhang et al., 2024); thus, deposition rates remained below 10 mg/cm²/day.

Fig. 16. Average 5-day silica scaling rates for the evaluated samples under simulated geothermal conditions.

Under cold conditions that trigger extreme scaling, it was observed that the scaling rate at a 0° (horizontal) inclination was higher than at 45° (inclined) for all samples. For example, the bare substrate recorded 262 mg/cm²/day at 0° versus 187.86 mg/cm²/day at 45°. This reduction at 45° is attributed to the higher shear stress exerted on the inclined surface, which effectively prevents adhesion and washes away newly formed silica nuclei. The scaling rates varied significantly among the four samples due to differences in hydrophobicity (WCA) and surface morphology. The A2 formulation (WCA 136.9°) recorded the lowest rate (128.58 mg/cm²/day under Cold 0°), while the hydrophilic substrate and neat epoxy recorded the highest rates (262 and 256.58 mg/cm²/day, respectively), confirming that hydrophobicity serves as the primary mitigation mechanism.

Despite the inherent hydrophobicity of the A3 nanocomposite, a significant disparity in scaling kinetics was observed, with A3 exhibiting a substantially higher accumulation rate (173.43 mg/cm²/day) compared to the 128.58 mg/cm²/day recorded for the A2 variant under identical Cold 0° conditions. This discrepancy is primarily attributed to the critical role of surface topography in modulating the interfacial interaction between the aqueous silica and the substrate. The A2 composite, characterized by a lower surface roughness (4.945 μm), facilitates the maintenance of a stable Cassie-Baxter state (Lotus effect), wherein trapped air pockets minimize the solid-liquid contact area and inhibit the initial attachment of silica nuclei, as illustrated in Figure 17a (van den Heuvel et al., 2020).

Conversely, the elevated and potentially inhomogeneous roughness of the A3 sample (13.277 μm) likely induces a transition toward a Wenzel state, where the liquid droplets penetrate deep into the surface asperities. This increased effective surface area and the presence of micro-scale "traps" serve to stabilize silica scale nuclei during the nucleation and growth stages (as depicted in Figure 17b), thereby accelerating the merging process into a continuous scale layer. Consequently, despite its chemical hydrophobicity, the excessive rugosity of A3

promotes rapid scale propagation by providing a higher density of favorable sites for heterogeneous nucleation (Azimi et al., 2014).

Fig. 17. Mechanism of silica scaling rates on: (a). rough and, (b). smooth surfaces.

The calculated percentage reduction in silica scaling rates demonstrates that the coating consistently provides superior performance compared to the steel substrate across all testing conditions, achieving peak mitigation under stable thermal conditions. The most significant reductions in scaling occurred under hot temperature at 45° (65.08%) and hot at 0° (59.88%) conditions, affirming that the hydrophobic properties of the A2 surface are highly effective at preventing silica attachment when natural scaling tendencies are lower. Despite the drastic increase in scaling rates under cold conditions, the A2 coating still successfully achieved a substantial reduction, with a 50.92% decrease at cold 0° and 41.59% at cold 45°. This proves that the optimized Epoxy/CNT/PTFE coating is capable of maintaining robust anti-scaling efficacy even when the fluid is in a state of high supersaturation.

4. Conclusion

In this study, the synergistic interplay between polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) within an epoxy matrix was successfully exploited to develop a multifunctional hybrid nanocomposite coating tailored for harsh geothermal environments.

The comprehensive characterization of these coatings revealed a definitive structure-property relationship governed by the balance between surface energy and morphological hierarchy. The incorporation of the hybrid fillers fundamentally drove the transition from a hydrophilic state to a robust hydrophobic regime. While extreme superhydrophobicity, characterized by a water contact angle (WCA) of 151.56° and a peak surface roughness (Ra) of $13.277\ \mu\text{m}$, was achieved at higher filler loadings (sample A3) via the Cassie-Baxter model, mechanical evaluations highlighted a critical optimization threshold. Excessive nanoparticle loading induced severe agglomeration, acting as structural defects that impeded polymer cross-linking and degraded interfacial bonding. Consequently, the Epoxy/PTFE40/CNT0.8 formulation (sample A2) was established as the optimal configuration. This formulation achieved a delicate equilibrium, delivering a stable Lotus effect (WCA of 139°) alongside superior mechanical integrity, which was evidenced by a peak adhesion strength of $8.685\ \text{MPa}$ facilitated by the load-transfer and crack-bridging mechanisms of the dispersed CNT network.

Concurrently, simultaneous thermal analysis (STA) demonstrated a fundamental shift in the thermal degradation mechanisms of the nanocomposites. A competitive thermodynamic interplay was introduced by the hybrid fillers; although the specific depolymerization of PTFE lowered the initial decomposition threshold, the integrated CNT network effectively counteracted this vulnerability by serving as a robust physical diffusion barrier. This synergy successfully modified the decomposition pathway into a stabilized two-stage process, promoting the formation of a protective carbonaceous char layer that yielded a residual mass exceeding 40 wt%. Ultimately, the structural and thermal integrity of the optimized coating was proven to be highly resilient, maintaining operational stability and thermal resistance at continuous exposure temperatures up to 150°C , with a maximum safe operational threshold established below 300°C to prevent primary chain scission.

The functional superiority of the optimized A2 coating was most prominently validated through its exceptional electrochemical and anti-scaling performances. Tafel polarization and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) confirmed that the composite established a dense, highly tortuous physical barrier against corrosive Cl^- ions. This morphological compactness suppressed electron transfer processes at the metallic interface, resulting in a peak charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of 882.9Ω (a 47% increase over the neat epoxy) and a minimal corrosion rate of 0.0098 mm/year , culminating in a superior protection efficiency of 94.05%. Furthermore, this optimal micro-topography proved highly effective in mitigating silica scaling. The A2 formulation consistently outperformed both the bare steel substrate and the excessively rough A3 sample, achieving peak scaling reductions of 65.08% under hot geothermal conditions and maintaining a robust 50.92% mitigation efficacy even under extreme cold supersaturation. The investigation elucidated that while the excessive roughness in sample A3 created "dead spots" that physically trapped and stabilized silica nuclei, the smoother topography of A2 prevented the mechanical interlocking of mineral deposits. Coupled with the effects of fluid dynamics where increased shear stress applied at a 45° inclination further inhibited scale adhesion and washed away silica clusters the optimized surface successfully repelled sustained mineral deposition.

In summary, the development of the Epoxy/PTFE40/CNT0.8 nanocomposite represents a significant advancement in protective barrier technologies. By achieving an optimal balance between hierarchical micro-roughness, high-impedance barrier integrity, and robust thermal stability, this hybrid coating provides a highly durable, multifunctional solution to simultaneously combat the dual threats of localized corrosion and mineral scaling, thereby offering a highly prospective strategy for extending the operational lifespan of geothermal infrastructure.

Acknowledgments

This research is funded by the Indonesian Endowment Fund for Education (LPDP) on behalf of the Indonesian Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology and managed under the INSPIRASI Program (Grant No. 2924/E3/AL.04/2024 dan 4809/UN1.P/HK.08.00/2024). We also thank the National Research and Innovation Agency (BRIN) for providing access to their testing facilities.

References

- Afolabi, O.A., Ndou, N., 2024. Synergy of Hybrid Fillers for Emerging Composite and Nanocomposite Materials—A Review. *Polymers (Basel)*. 16, 1907.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16131907>
- Alsaleh, M., Yang, Z., Chen, T., Wang, X., Abdul-Rahim, A.S., Mahmood, H., 2023. Moving toward environmental sustainability: Assessing the influence of geothermal power on carbon dioxide emissions. *Renew. Energy* 202, 880–893.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.11.060>
- Andrameda, Y.A., Kusmono, Khasani, Kurniawan, H.A., Febrianto, H.A., 2026. Optimization and characterization of high-performance superhydrophobic epoxy/PTFE/CNT hybrid nanocomposite coatings. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology* 41, 6390–6407. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2026.02.163>
- Ashraf, M.A., Peng, W., Zare, Y., Rhee, K.Y., 2018. Effects of Size and Aggregation/Agglomeration of Nanoparticles on the Interfacial/Interphase Properties and Tensile Strength of Polymer Nanocomposites. *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 13, 214.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s11671-018-2624-0>

- Azimi, G., Cui, Y., Sabanska, A., Varanasi, K.K., 2014. Scale-resistant surfaces: Fundamental studies of the effect of surface energy on reducing scale formation. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 313, 591–599.
- Badea, G.E., Caraban, A., Sebesan, M., Dzitac, S., Cret, P., Setel, A., 2010. Polarisation measurements used for corrosion rates determination. *Journal of sustainable energy* 1, 1.
- Bandeira, C.F., Montoro, S.R., Faria, S.T., Moreira, P.R.S., Pereira, A.C.C., Oliveira, L.F., Milanese, A.C., 2017. Degradability of Epoxy/Sisal Fiber Composites via Simulated Soil. *Journal of Research Updates in Polymer Science* 6, 12–16.
<https://doi.org/10.6000/1929-5995.2017.06.01.2>
- Bao, X., Wu, F., Wang, J., 2021. Thermal degradation behavior of epoxy resin containing modified carbon nanotubes. *Polymers (Basel)*. 13, 3332.
- Bhuvanendran Nair Jayakumari, A., Malik, N.G., Mittal, G., Martelo, D., Kale, N., Paul, S., 2023. A Review on Geothermal Heat Exchangers: Challenges, Coating Methods, and Coating Materials. *Coatings*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings13121988>
- Boakye, G.O., Straume, E.O., Kovalov, D., Karlsdottir, Prof.S.N., 2022. Wear-Reducing Nickel-Phosphorus and Graphene Oxide-Based Composite Coatings: Microstructure and Corrosion Behavior in High Temperature Geothermal Environment. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4211395>
- Burstein, G.T., Vines, S.P., 2001. Repetitive Nucleation of Corrosion Pits on Stainless Steel and the Effects of Surface Roughness. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 148, B504.
<https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1416503>

- Chopra, I., Ola, S.K., Dhayal, V., Shekhawat, D.S., 2022. Recent advances in epoxy coatings for corrosion protection of steel: Experimental and modelling approach-A review. *Mater. Today Proc.* 62, 1658–1663.
- Dacillo, K.B., Zarrouk, S.J., 2023. Stress Corrosion Cracking in Metal Alloys Exposed to Geothermal Fluids with High Non-Condensable Gas Content. *Geothermics* 111, 102724. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2023.102724>
- Deflorian, F., Rossi, S., 2006. An EIS study of ion diffusion through organic coatings. *Electrochim. Acta* 51, 1736–1744.
- Deflorian, F., Rossi, S., Fedel, M., Motte, C., 2010. Electrochemical investigation of high-performance silane sol-gel films containing clay nanoparticles. *Prog. Org. Coat.* 69, 158–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2010.04.007>
- Deyab, M.A., Awadallah, A.E., 2020. Advanced anticorrosive coatings based on epoxy/functionalized multiwall carbon nanotubes composites. *Prog. Org. Coat.* 139, 105423. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2019.105423>
- Experience Efeosa Akhigbe, 2025. Advancing geothermal energy: A review of technological developments and environmental impacts. *Gulf Journal of Advance Business Research* 3, 700–711. <https://doi.org/10.51594/gjabr.v3i2.104>
- Fan, L., Li, B., Wang, Y., He, J., Bai, J., Zhu, T., Yuan, Y., 2023. Superhydrophobic Epoxy/Fluorosilicone/PTFE Coatings Prepared by One-Step Spraying for Enhanced Anti-Icing Performance. *Coatings* 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings13030569>
- Fanicchia, F., Karlsdottir, S.N., 2023. Research and Development on Coatings and Paints for Geothermal Environments: A Review. *Adv. Mater. Technol.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202202031>

- Gu, A., Liang, G., 2003. Thermal degradation behaviour and kinetic analysis of epoxy/montmorillonite nanocomposites. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 80, 383–391.
- Han, Z., Tay, B., Tan, C., Shakerzadeh, M., Ostrikov, K., 2009. Electrowetting control of Cassie-to-Wenzel transitions in superhydrophobic carbon nanotube-based nanocomposites. *ACS Nano* 3, 3031–3036.
- Hassani, K., Zheng, W., 2025. A review of recent advances in mineral scaling in geothermal energy systems: mechanisms, mitigation, and case studies. *Environ. Earth Sci.* 84, 418. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-025-12416-9>
- Hernández, H.H., Reynoso, A.M.R., González, J.C.T., Morán, C.O.G., Hernández, J.G.M., Ruiz, A.M., Hernández, J.M., Cruz, R.O., 2020. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS): A review study of basic aspects of the corrosion mechanism applied to steels. *Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy* 137–144.
- Huang, X., Yang, C., Chen, J., Qiao, X., Zhang, S., Song, D., 2024. Enhanced Protective Performance of Carbon Nanotube-Reinforced Waterborne Epoxy Zinc-Rich Coatings for Corrosion Protection of Steel Structures. *Coatings* 14, 1493. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings14121493>
- Ishmah, S.N., Permana, M.D., Firdaus, M.L., Eddy, D.R., 2020. Extraction of silica from bengkulu beach sand using alkali fusion method. *PENDIPA Journal of Science Education* 4, 1–5.
- Jeon, H., Park, J., Shon, M., 2013. Corrosion protection by epoxy coating containing multi-walled carbon nanotubes. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 19, 849–853.

- Jung, K.K., Jung, Y., Choi, C.J., Ko, J.S., 2018. Highly Reliable Superhydrophobic Surface with Carbon Nanotubes Immobilized on a PDMS/Adhesive Multilayer. *ACS Omega* 3, 12956–12966. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.7b01872>
- Karlsdottir, S.N., Manadao Bravo, A., Boakye, G.O., Pálsson, H., Stefánsson, A., 2023. Corrosion Testing of Coatings in Simulated ORC Geothermal Heat Exchanger Environment, in: CONFERENCE 2023. AMPP, pp. 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5006/C2023-19444>
- Khasani, Kusmono, Utami, P., Budiarto, R., 2021. Corrosion in geothermal facilities: Their causes, effects, mitigation, and worldwide cases. p. 020007. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0066755>
- Kim, H. Bin, Lee, W.J., Choi, S.C., Lee, K.B., Lee, M.-H., 2021. Preparation of PTFE-glass composite filter with low surface free energy by sandblasting. *Surfaces and Interfaces* 26, 101381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2021.101381>
- Levchik, S. V, Weil, E.D., 2004. Thermal decomposition, combustion and flame-retardancy of epoxy resins—a review of the recent literature. *Polym. Int.* 53, 1901–1929. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pi.1473>
- Li, C., Long, J., Li, Y., Feng, Z., 2023. Tensile Property and Toughening Mechanism of Nanoparticle-Modified Epoxy Adhesive. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering* 35. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0004747](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0004747)
- Li, Z., Qi, X., Liu, C., Fan, B., Yang, X., 2023. Particle size effect of PTFE on friction and wear properties of glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin composites. *Wear* 532, 205104.

- Lichti, K.A., Ghaziof, S., Julian, R., Mountain, B.W., 2024. Geochemical modelling of heavy metal deposition in a geothermal heat exchanger. *Geothermics* 118, 102884.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2023.102884>
- Liu, Y., Gao, G., Jiang, D., Yin, Z., 2022. Enhancement of Underwater Tribological Properties of Hybrid PTFE/Nomex Fabric/Epoxy Resin Multilayer Composites by Mixed Graphite and MoS Fillers. *ACS Omega* 7, 27609–27616.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c03231>
- Liu, Y., Wang, J., Liu, L., Li, Y., Wang, F., 2013. Study of the failure mechanism of an epoxy coating system under high hydrostatic pressure. *Corros. Sci.* 74, 59–70.
- Longval, R., Meirbekova, R., Fisher, J., Maignot, A., 2024. An Overview of Silica Scaling Reduction Technologies in the Geothermal Market. *Energies (Basel)*. 17, 4825.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/en17194825>
- Loureiro, J.B.R., Martins, A.L., Gonçalves, A.S., Souza, B.G.B., Schluter, H.E.P., Santos, H.F.L., Castro, B.B., Pepe, I.M., Soares Junior, L.C.S., Demetino, G.G., 2023. Large-scale pipe flow experiments for the evaluation of nonchemical solutions for calcium carbonate scaling inhibition and control. *SPE Journal* 28, 201–214.
- Martelo, D., Holmes, B., Kale, N., Scott, S.W., Paul, S., 2024. Investigation of Scaling and Materials' Performance in Simulated Geothermal Brine. *Materials* 17, 5250.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ma17215250>
- Medvedovski, E., 2020. Advanced iron boride coatings to enhance corrosion resistance of steels in geothermal power generation. *Advances in Applied Ceramics* 119, 462–481.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/17436753.2020.1830359>

- Mirzapour, M., Cousin, P., Robert, M., Benmokrane, B., 2024. Dispersion Characteristics, the Mechanical, Thermal Stability, and Durability Properties of Epoxy Nanocomposites Reinforced with Carbon Nanotubes, Graphene, or Graphene Oxide. *Polymers (Basel)*. 16, 1836. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16131836>
- Morita, K., Gonzales, J., Sakaue, H., 2018. Effect of PTFE Particle Size on Superhydrophobic Coating for Supercooled Water Prevention. *Coatings* 8, 426. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings8120426>
- Nogara, J., Zarrouk, S.J., 2018. Corrosion in geothermal environment: Part 1: Fluids and their impact. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 82, 1333–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.06.098>
- Oppong Boakye, G., Straume, E.O., Gunnarsson, B.G., Kovalov, D., Karlsdottir, S.N., 2023. Corrosion behaviour of HVOF developed Mo-based high entropy alloy coating and selected hard coatings for high temperature geothermal applications. *Mater. Des.* 235, 112431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2023.112431>
- Pan, C., Kou, K., Jia, Q., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Wu, G., Feng, A., 2016. Fabrication and characterization of micro-nano AlN co-filled PTFE composites with enhanced thermal conductivity: a morphology-promoted synergistic effect. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Electronics* 27, 11909–11916. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10854-016-5336-1>
- Parry, V., Berthomé, G., Joud, J.-C., 2012. Wetting properties of gas diffusion layers: Application of the Cassie–Baxter and Wenzel equations. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 258, 5619–5627. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2012.02.038>
- Penot, C., Martelo, D., Paul, S., 2023. Corrosion and Scaling in Geothermal Heat Exchangers. *Applied Sciences* 13, 11549. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app132011549>

- Qian, D., Dickey, E.C., Andrews, R., Rantell, T., 2000. Load transfer and deformation mechanisms in carbon nanotube-polystyrene composites. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 76, 2868–2870. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.126500>
- Rachid, H.B., Nouredine, D., Benali, B., Adin, M.Ş., 2024. Effect of nanocomposites rate on the crack propagation in the adhesive of single lap joint subjected to tension. *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures* 31, 6898–6906. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15376494.2023.2240319>
- Ramakrishnan, T., Raja Karthikeyan, K., Tamilselvan, V., Sivakumar, S., Gangodkar, D., Radha, H.R., Narain Singh, A., Asrat Waji, Y., 2022. Study of Various Epoxy-Based Surface Coating Techniques for Anticorrosion Properties. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering* 2022, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5285919>
- Sahli, M., Cablé, A., Chetehouna, K., Hamamda, S., Gascoin, N., Revo, S., 2017. Preparation and characterization of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)/Thermally Expanded Graphite (TEG) nanocomposites. *Compos. B Eng.* 124, 175–181.
- Satish, G., Prasad, V.V.S., Ramji, K., 2017. Manufacturing and characterization of CNT based polymer composites. *Mathematical Models in Engineering* 3, 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.21595/mme.2017.19121>
- Serroune, S.A., Ugm, K., Kakiecwski, J., Brenton, M., Serroune5, A., Basset, D., Serroune, H., Gescot, S., 2024. Development and Characterization of Advanced Nano-Coating with CeO₂, Al₂O₃, ZnO, and TiO₂ Nanoparticles for Enhanced Durability and Corrosion Resistance. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v12i10.mp05>
- Shannon, D.W., 1975. Economic impact of corrosion and scaling problems in geothermal energy systems. Richland, WA. <https://doi.org/10.2172/5122645>

- Spinthaki, A., Kamaratou, M., Skordalou, G., Petratos, G., Petrou, I., Tramaux, A., David, G., Demadis, K.D., 2021. Searching for a universal scale inhibitor: A multi-scale approach towards inhibitor efficiency. *Geothermics* 89, 101954.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2020.101954>
- Sugama, T., Gawlik, K., 2002. Anti-silica fouling coatings in geothermal environments. *Mater. Lett.* 57, 666–673. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-577X\(02\)00851-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-577X(02)00851-0)
- Suroń, P., Białkowska, A., Bakar, M., Hanulikova, B., Masař, M., Kroisová, D., 2025. Ternary Epoxy Nanocomposites with Synergistic Effects: Preparation, Properties Evaluation and Structure Analysis. *Polymers (Basel)*. 17, 158.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17020158>
- Torrecillas, R., Baudry, A., Dufay, J., Mortaigne, B., 1996. Thermal degradation of high performance polymers—influence of structure on polyimide thermostability. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 54, 267–274. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(96\)00052-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(96)00052-3)
- van den Heuvel, D.B., Gunnlaugsson, E., Benning, L.G., 2020. Surface roughness affects early stages of silica scale formation more strongly than chemical and structural properties of the substrate. *Geothermics* 87, 101835.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2020.101835>
- Van den Heuvel, D.B., Gunnlaugsson, E., Gunnarsson, I., Stawski, T.M., Peacock, C.L., Benning, L.G., 2018. Understanding amorphous silica scaling under well-constrained conditions inside geothermal pipelines. *Geothermics* 76, 231–241.
- Vicente, I., Salagre, P., Cesteros, Y., 2010. Preparation of pure hectorite using microwaves. *Phys. Procedia* 8, 88–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phpro.2010.10.017>

- Xie, J., Chen, K., Yan, M., Guo, J., Xie, Q., Lü, F., 2022. Effect of temperature and water penetration on the interfacial bond between epoxy resin and glass fiber: A molecular dynamics study. *J. Mol. Liq.* 350, 118424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2021.118424>
- Ying, L., Wu, Y., Nie, C., Wu, C., Wang, G., 2020. Improvement of the Tribological Properties and Corrosion Resistance of Epoxy–PTFE Composite Coating by Nanoparticle Modification. *Coatings* 11, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings11010010>
- Zarrouk, S.J., Moon, H., 2014. Efficiency of geothermal power plants: A worldwide review. *Geothermics* 51, 142–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2013.11.001>
- Zarrouk, S.J., Woodhurst, B.C., Morris, C., 2014. Silica scaling in geothermal heat exchangers and its impact on pressure drop and performance: Wairakei binary plant, New Zealand. *Geothermics* 51, 445–459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2014.03.005>
- Zeinedini, A., Akhavan-Safar, A., da Silva, L.F.M., 2025. The role of agglomeration in the physical properties of CNTs/polymer nanocomposites: A literature review. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part L: Journal of Materials: Design and Applications*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14644207251316470>
- Zhang, F., Qian, H., Wang, L., Wang, Z., Du, C., Li, X., Zhang, D., 2018. Superhydrophobic carbon nanotubes/epoxy nanocomposite coating by facile one-step spraying. *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 341, 15–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2018.01.045>
- Zhang, F., Zhou, W., Ullah, M.Z., Ma, Y., Liu, M., 2020. CONVECTION SCALING ON MODIFIED SURFACES OF PLATE HEAT EXCHANGER IN 80°C SIMULATED GEOTHERMAL WATER. *Interfacial Phenom. Heat Transf.* 8, 117–133. <https://doi.org/10.1615/InterfacPhenomHeatTransfer.2020031915>

- Zhang, H., You, W., Bian, F., Yu, W., 2022. Heterogeneous Percolation in Poly(methylvinylsiloxane)/Silica Nanocomposites: The Role of Polymer–Particle Interaction. *Macromolecules* 55, 8834–8845. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.macromol.2c01615>
- Zhang, R., Yang, K., Dang, B., Zhan, M., Zhang, P., Li, S., 2024. Anti-Corrosion and Wave-Absorbing Properties of Epoxy-Based Coatings on Q235 Steel. *Coatings* 14, 1315.
- Zhang, Z., Tang, S., Ge, K., Wang, K., Ji, Y., 2024. High-Efficiency Terpolymer Scale Inhibitor for Obstructing the Formation of Calcium Sulfate by Preventing Crystallization. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 63, 11463–11471.
- Zhang, Z., Zhang, H., Lv, W., Zhang, J., Wang, N., 2021. Micro-structure characteristics of unsaturated polyester resin modified concrete under fatigue loads and hygrothermal environment. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 296, 123766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.123766>
- Zhao, H., Huang, Y., Deng, S., Wang, L., Peng, H., Shen, X., Ling, D., Liu, L., Liu, Y., 2023. Research progress on scaling mechanism and anti-scaling technology of geothermal well system. *J. Dispers. Sci. Technol.* 44, 1657–1670. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01932691.2022.2033625>
- Zheng, X., Li, D., Feng, C., Chen, X., 2015. Thermal properties and non-isothermal curing kinetics of carbon nanotubes/ionic liquid/epoxy resin systems. *Thermochim. Acta* 618, 18–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2015.09.007>
- Zhi, D., Wang, H., Jiang, D., Parkin, I.P., Zhang, X., 2019. Reactive silica nanoparticles turn epoxy coating from hydrophilic to super-robust superhydrophobic. *RSC Adv.* 9, 12547–12554. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8RA10046B>